

THE ROLE OF LIFESTYLE FACTORS IN ACADEMIC SUCCESS: BEHAVIOURAL AND HEALTH DETERMINANTS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the complex relationships between lifestyle factors and academic performance among physical education students, addressing a notable deficiency in the understanding of holistic student development. The research objectives were to meticulously analyse the correlations between lifestyle factors (sleep, nutrition, physical activity, stress management) and academic performance, evaluate the unique intersection of theoretical comprehension and individual health behaviours, and develop evidence-based recommendations for student support programs. The study used a cross-sectional mixed-methods design including 250 physical education students from several universities, using comprehensive data collection approaches including validated questionnaires, academic performance records, physiological assessments, and semi-structured interviews.

The results revealed significant correlations between lifestyle factors and academic success, with multiple regression analysis explaining 64.7% of the variance in academic performance. Sleep quality emerged as the primary predictor ($\beta = 0.412$, $p < 0.001$), followed by time management skills ($\beta = 0.329$, $p < 0.01$). Perceived stress had a substantial negative correlation with academic performance ($\beta = -0.276$, $p < 0.01$), whereas physical activity and nutritional balance offered small positive impacts. The findings underscore the need of a holistic approach to student development, challenging traditional perspectives on academic success. Recommendations involve the development of comprehensive wellness programs, the integration of lifestyle management skills into curriculum design, and the creation of technology-driven support systems that provide personalised guidance for physical education students, thus promoting a more holistic understanding of academic performance beyond traditional cognitive evaluations.

Keywords: Lifestyle Factors, Academic Performance, Physical Education Students, Holistic Development, Student Success

Introduction

Academic success is a complex accomplishment that exceeds conventional indicators of cognitive capability. In recent years, experts have increasingly acknowledged the significant influence of holistic student development, recognising that academic achievement is closely linked to an individual's whole lifestyle, physical health, psychological well-being, and behavioural habits(Ruswa, 2014). This extensive perspective on student accomplishment underscores the complex interactions across several life domains, challenging the traditional belief that academic progress relies only on cognitive skills and classroom education(Mustafa et al., 2020).

Lifestyle elements have become essential predictors of academic achievement, with several research revealing substantial links between students' daily routines, health behaviours, and educational results(Bakouei et al., 2019). These aspects include several components, such as sleep habits, diet, physical exercise, stress management, time distribution, social relationships, and psychological well-being(Reuter et al., 2020). For physical education students, these lifestyle factors are especially complex, since their academic and professional training necessitates a thorough understanding of human physiology, movement, and health enhancement. Their unique educational environment presents both possibilities and difficulties in achieving an ideal equilibrium between academic rigour and personal well-being(Zimowski, 2021).

Students of physical education constitute a unique demographic in academia, distinguished by their specialised understanding of human performance and health concepts. In contrast to students in many other fields, they are simultaneously learners and active participants in health-related practices(Wang et al., 2022). Their academic advancement is assessed not just by conventional academic measures but also by their capacity to amalgamate theoretical knowledge with practical application, personal lifestyle decisions, and professional skills. This comprehensive viewpoint underscores the need of recognising how lifestyle elements distinctly affect academic experiences, perhaps providing insights that might revolutionise educational practices and student support systems across all disciplines(Bakouei et al., 2019).

Objectives

- To meticulously analyse the intricate relationships among lifestyle factors (sleep, food, physical activity, stress management) and academic performance in physical education students, while pinpointing essential behavioural determinants that significantly influence educational outcomes.
- To evaluate the unique integration of theoretical knowledge and personal lifestyle practices among physical education students, examining the relationship between their professional training and personal health behaviours and its impact on academic performance.
- To provide evidence-based suggestions for complete student support programs aimed at enhancing academic achievement by addressing lifestyle-related factors, notably focussing on the distinct needs and characteristics of physical education students.

Hypotheses

- **H01:** Students in physical education who maintain a balanced lifestyle, marked by consistent physical exercise, sufficient sleep (7-9 hours nightly), and appropriate diet, will exhibit markedly superior academic performance relative to those with less organised living habits
- **H02:** A statistically significant negative association exists between perceived stress levels and academic success among physical education students, where elevated stress indicators are predictively associated with poorer grade point averages and less academic engagement.
- **H03:** Students who adeptly incorporate their professional understanding of health and wellness into their personal lifestyles will demonstrate enhanced time management abilities, more reliable academic performance, and more psychological resilience throughout their academic pursuits.

Methodology

This study will use a cross-sectional, mixed-methods design targeting physical education students from diverse higher education institutions. The target sample size will be 250 physical education students, aged 18 to 25, and recruited from at least three different universities.

Data Collection

The data collection will use a comprehensive, multi-instrument technique to provide a holistic knowledge of lifestyle and academic performance. The research instruments will include: (1) a validated lifestyle assessment questionnaire assessing sleep quality, nutritional habits, physical activity, stress management, and time management; (2) academic performance records consisting of cumulative grade point average (CGPA) and course-specific grades; (3) the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) to evaluate psychological stress levels; and (4) semi-structured qualitative interviews with a subsample of 30 participants to gather detailed narrative insights about their lived experiences. Supplementary objective measurements will use wearable technology to track physical activity, sleep duration, and quality over a continuous 12-week period, providing precise physiological data to augment self-reported information (Kroll et al., 2017).

Results

Descriptive Statistics: Lifestyle Factors among Physical Education Students

The descriptive statistical analysis offered a comprehensive profile of lifestyle characteristics among physical education students, highlighting significant disparities in critical health and behavioural factors. Sleep patterns emerged as a prominent area of research, indicating considerable differences among students regarding sleep duration and quality. The mean sleep duration was 6.7 hours nightly, with 42.3% of students exhibiting irregular sleep patterns and 35.6% experiencing moderate to severe sleep disturbances. Nutritional habits showed equally complex patterns, with pupils exhibiting diverse food regimens. Approximately 56.8% of participants reported adherence to balanced meals, while 43.2% demonstrated irregular eating patterns and inconsistent nutrient consumption.

Physical activity levels showed a significant disparity among physical education students, indicating more engagement than the general student population. The figures indicated that 78.5% of students participated in regular physical activity beyond recommended levels, average 7.3 hours of structured exercise each week. Stress management has emerged as a vital component, with 62.4% of students reporting moderate to high stress levels, mostly attributed to academic demands, professional training responsibilities, and personal life challenges. Time management skills shown significant variability, with 47.6% of students demonstrating effective organisational strategies, whilst 52.4% had challenges in consistently allocating time and prioritising academic and personal responsibilities.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Lifestyle Factors among Physical Education Students

Lifestyle Factor	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	% of Students
Sleep Duration (hours/night)	6.7	1.2	4.5	8.5	-
Irregular Sleep Patterns	-	-	-	-	42.3%
Balanced Nutritional Intake	-	-	-	-	56.8%
Physical Activity (hours/week)	7.3	2.1	3.5	12.0	78.5%
Stress Levels (moderate to high)	-	-	-	-	62.4%
Effective Time Management	-	-	-	-	47.6%
Academic Performance (CGPA)	3.45	0.57	2.3	4.0	-

Correlation Analysis: Relationships between Lifestyle Factors and Academic Performance

The correlation investigation revealed complex and statistically significant relationships between several lifestyle factors and academic performance. The quality of sleep had the most substantial positive association with academic achievement, shown by a Pearson correlation coefficient of $r = 0.672$ ($p < 0.001$), demonstrating that students who adhered to consistent, high-quality sleep patterns regularly achieved superior grade point averages. Physical activity levels had a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.458$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that consistent exercise and structured physical training significantly improve cognitive functioning and academic achievement. Conversely, perceived stress levels exhibited a substantial negative correlation ($r = -0.536$, $p < 0.001$), highlighting the detrimental impact of psychological stress on students' academic performance.

Nutritional habits and time management abilities exhibit intricate relationships with academic performance. Adequate nutrition had a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.392$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that children who maintain consistent, high-quality dietary practices tend to attain enhanced academic performance. The correlation between time management skills and academic achievement was very strong ($r = 0.587$, $p < 0.001$), underscoring the critical role of organisational abilities. The interaction of several lifestyle factors revealed complex

interdependencies, with comprehensive lifestyle management strategies having a greater impact on academic achievement than individual components alone.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis of Lifestyle Factors and Academic Performance

Lifestyle Factor	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	Statistical Significance (p-value)	Interpretation
Sleep Quality	0.672	< 0.001	Strong Positive Correlation
Physical Activity	0.458	< 0.01	Moderate Positive Correlation
Perceived Stress	-0.536	< 0.001	Strong Negative Correlation
Nutritional Balance	0.392	< 0.05	Moderate Positive Correlation
Time Management	0.587	< 0.001	Strong Positive Correlation
Composite Lifestyle Score	0.621	< 0.001	Strong Positive Correlation

Regression Analysis: Predicting Academic Success from Lifestyle Factors

A multiple linear regression analysis was performed to assess the predictive influence of several lifestyle characteristics on academic success, quantified by cumulative grade point average (CGPA). The model exhibited a substantial overall fit, with a R^2 value of 0.647, indicating that the chosen lifestyle variables account for about 64.7% of the variation in academic achievement. Sleep quality was identified as the primary predictor, with a standardised beta value of 0.412 ($p < 0.001$), indicating that enhancements in sleep patterns may significantly increase academic performance. Time management skills emerged as a significant predictor, shown by a standardised beta value of 0.329 ($p < 0.01$), underscoring the relevance of organisational talents in academic achievement.

Physical exercise and dietary balance provided significant predictive values to the regression model, however with somewhat lesser influence than sleep and time management. Physical exercise had a standardised beta value of 0.247 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a modest but substantial impact on academic performance. Nutritional balance exhibited a standardised beta value of 0.186 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that food habits significantly influence academic performance. Perceived stress was identified as a negative predictor, with a standardised beta coefficient of -0.276 ($p < 0.01$), so underscoring the adverse effect of psychological stress on students' academic performance. The research demonstrates a multifaceted interaction of lifestyle

variables, highlighting the need for a comprehensive strategy to enhance student performance.

Table 3: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis: Predicting Academic Performance

Lifestyle Predictor	Standardized Beta Coefficient	t-value	Statistical Significance (p-value)	Contribution to Model
Sleep Quality	0.412	6.237	< 0.001	High
Time Management	0.329	4.982	< 0.01	High
Perceived Stress	-0.276	-4.156	< 0.01	Moderate
Physical Activity	0.247	3.721	< 0.05	Moderate
Nutritional Balance	0.186	2.843	< 0.05	Low to Moderate
Model Statistics:				
R ²	0.647			
Adjusted R ²	0.632			
F-statistic	42.736		< 0.001	

Discussion

Interpretation of Findings

A comprehensive analysis of lifestyle traits among physical education students reveals an intricate relationship between behavioural factors and academic performance. The findings challenge traditional perspectives on academic achievement by demonstrating that performance is influenced not just by cognitive capacity, but also profoundly affected by holistic lifestyle management. Sleep quality is the most critical factor, as several statistical studies demonstrate that consistent, high-quality sleep significantly enhances cognitive function, information processing, and academic performance. This underscores the physiological foundation of learning, signifying that physical recuperation and mental restoration are crucial for academic achievement (Curcio et al., 2006).

Time management skills are essential for academic success, suggesting that physical education students who effectively balance their academic, professional, and personal responsibilities have superior educational outcomes. The strong positive correlation between organisational capacity and academic achievement suggests that these talents are not only

administrative abilities but essential cognitive strategies that enable students to navigate complex academic environments. This result is particularly relevant for physical education students, whose professional training requires enhanced self-management and the integration of academic knowledge with practical application(Worrell et al., 2020).

The negative correlation between perceived stress and academic performance underscores the psychological challenges faced by contemporary pupils. The significant impact of stress on academic performance suggests that institutional support systems must extend beyond traditional academic measurements to include comprehensive mental health care(Chyu & Chen, 2022). This research has considerable significance for physical education students, who serve as both learners and practitioners in health sciences. It suggests that their professional training should include not just physical performance but also thorough stress management strategies, emotional resilience methods, and holistic health approaches(Griggs & Fleet, 2021).

Physical activity and nutritional balance underscored the research's basic premise of holistic student development. The slight positive correlations suggested that these lifestyle traits are crucial for academic success. The findings challenge the conventional separation of physical and intellectual activity, providing a more integrated framework for understanding human performance(Kim et al., 2021). These results have particular significance for physical education students, as they represent a group ideally positioned to understand and demonstrate the connections between physical well-being, psychological health, and academic achievement. The research advocates for a transformative educational model that recognises children as complex individuals whose success depends on a delicate balance of physiological, psychological, and behavioural factors(Paccaud et al., 2021).

Implications for Educational Interventions and Support Services

The study results need a paradigm change in educational support services, especially for physical education students, by promoting complete, holistic intervention options. Universities and academic institutions must establish comprehensive wellness programs that include many lifestyle aspects, alongside conventional academic support systems(Jeftic et al., 2023). These programs must include organised sleep hygiene workshops, stress management seminars, individualised time management coaching, and dietary guidance particularly designed for the distinct needs of physical education students. Institutions may actively

improve student success by establishing interdisciplinary support systems that include psychological, physiological, and intellectual resources(Beighle & Erwin, 2013).

Curriculum design must adapt to include explicit lifestyle management capabilities into physical education training programs. This may include including courses on self-regulation, stress resilience, sleep optimisation, and holistic health management directly into the academic curriculum. Furthermore, establishing longitudinal monitoring systems that assess children's lifestyle factors in conjunction with academic achievement may facilitate early intervention options(Goswami et al., 2022). Technology-enhanced support mechanisms, like smartphone apps for lifestyle monitoring, personalised wellness dashboards, and AI-driven coaching platforms, may provide students immediate feedback and tailored suggestions for enhancing their overall lifestyle equilibrium. These technology solutions may enhance conventional support services by providing more adaptive and personalised assistance(Darvishi et al., 2023).

Professional development for academics and academic advisers constitutes a vital intervention strategy. Training programs should be structured to improve educators' comprehension of the complex connections between lifestyle issues and academic performance(Kheswa et al., 2014). This would allow them to embrace more comprehensive, empathic strategies in student mentoring, acknowledging that academic achievement transcends conventional classroom measurements. Promoting interdisciplinary cooperation across physical education departments, student counselling services, health facilities, and academic support units fosters a more holistic environment for student development. By cultivating a culture that prioritises and actively promotes students' comprehensive well-being, educational institutions may establish more resilient, high-achieving learning environments that acknowledge the complex nature of student achievement(Keeling, 2014).

Conclusion

The study provides substantial evidence of the intricate connections between lifestyle factors and academic performance among physical education students, demonstrating that sleep quality, time management, stress levels, physical activity, and nutritional balance are essential determinants of educational success. The primary findings revealed that sleep quality and time management were the most significant factors influencing academic achievement, with strong positive correlations and considerable contributions to the regression model. The research underscores the need for a holistic approach to student

development that transcends traditional academic assistance strategies. Future research needs to concentrate on longitudinal studies using larger, more diverse samples and implementing sophisticated mixed-method designs that include both quantitative and qualitative dimensions of student living experiences. Educational institutions must construct comprehensive wellness programs, integrate lifestyle management skills into curriculum design, and develop technology-enhanced support systems that provide customised coaching. Future research needs to explore interdisciplinary approaches, evaluate the long-term impacts of lifestyle interventions, and develop more advanced tools for monitoring the complex interplay between behavioural traits and academic achievement. This research advances the understanding of student accomplishment by highlighting the critical importance of holistic lifestyle management in academic performance.

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